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Operational guide for educational initiatives related to biodiversity practices in nature-based schoolyards aimed at school staff: from research to the learning field

WP2 Biodiversity practices transformations

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**Ideas for thinking about educational actions
for education stakeholders in schools
From research to the learning field**

Preamble

- These ideas have been devised for new educational initiatives in schools;
- These ideas are based on the latest work in the field of educational sciences in France*;
- The links between the proposed activity tracks and formal learning must be adapted according to the contexts.

* Voir l'ouvrage synthétique *Dictionnaire critique des enjeux et concepts des éducations à*, Angela Barthes, Jean-Marc Lange & Céline Chauvigné (Dir.), 2024, Paris, L'Harmattan.

Introduction

The framework proposed below aims to shed light on two fundamental questions that the transformation of schoolyards induces:

- What kind of change is advocated by educational sciences today and why?
- How can we make the link between theoretical recommendations and the concrete realities of the Oasis schoolyards?

Oasis schoolyards in a new world: support for change and a goal for change

Planned educational intent

1 conforming change

insertion

Existing situation unchanged, addition of sustainable development ideas, biodiversity...

2 reformative change

integration

Evolution of requirements through integration of cross-disciplinary skills (education to sustainable development, moral and civic education etc.)

3 transformative change

new paradigm

Thinking differently about education

Why educate differently today?

Integrating the **paradigm of rupture** in the face of upheavals in the Earth system that are unpredictable but must be predicted

- > thinking about change
- > taking actions

A global education that addresses **current issues** through education

From “education to...” (contextualized theoretical foundations) towards postures and actions

- starting with educational intentions : slides 10 to 30
- based on concrete material and facts from the courtyard that call for action: slides 31 to 38

Educational intentions to transform: two complementary paths

Transformative change in
our relationships with
learning places

scientific rationality

problem

The courtyard provides problems to be remedied.

survey

empathy

other humans

non-humans

future

Decide together what is desirable in and for the courtyard.

action

think to act

affect

solicitude

attention, benevolence

care

ethic of living

Double entry from the Oasis schoolyards, the important thing is to act!

From intentions to educational approaches

Transversal educational approaches

Importance of the sciences

- science
- rational story
- exploration

know

dream

- fantastic story
- imaginary

embellish

Thinking differently about the courtyard

appropriate > ATTENTION

- care
- empathy
- common goods

politicize > INTENTION

- action
- survey
- problem
- engagement

Prospective

politicizing the courtyard:
managing the common good

know

See and perceive the invisible or the unseen:
ruse to unearth, flush out, discover, guess, imagine...
with scientific, exploratory or literary approaches

Focus on science

- > intellectualizes reality, a process of abstraction and conceptualization that weaves together the visible and the invisible
 - > forces attention to the Other through the cognitive activity of guided observation.

Educate the curiosity: make yourself intellectually available to a given subject or phenomenon.

Educate to the biodiversity: goes beyond scientific education in biological diversity, carries ethical, political and economic dimensions beyond explanatory, analytical and historical dimensions > hybrid concept between science and governance

Biodiversity education deals with socially pressing issues

Explore

Unsuspected nature in the courtyard?

Naturalist inventories :

to see what's hidden (small animals)

to see what's too small (mini and micro worlds)

to perceive what's too big (what goes beyond the yard)

to perceive what's passing by (ephemeral visitors)

to guess who leaves traces (footprints, remains, clues, etc.)

➤ participatory science protocols

Nature Watch: Arthropods, Annelids, Mollusks...

Dare to discover a new space, adults and children exploring...

Step out of your comfort zone > become an explorer of the place

A teacher is not an expert. He/she accompanies and supervises children's discovery of the world around them. They provide students with the tools they need to understand and appropriate this place (math, French, science, technology, etc.). The aim is to question and understand the world around us - the classroom, the school, the neighborhood, the city... the world. He teaches risk-taking, otherness and empathy.

Exploring all scales of courtyard viewpoints: from landscape to the invisible

Courtyards in the near and distant world

The little worlds of the court

Between geography/history & science

Between imagination and

Essential skills: reading, writing, counting, measuring, drawing, moving...

Dream

According to philosopher Michel Foucault, heterotopia is possible in the courtyard: a “counter-space” where the dominant order can be challenged, where escape is possible through the production of imaginary worlds.

The presence of nature in the courtyard stimulates the imagination.

Setting the imagination in motion

Encouraging attachment, curiosity and wonder - building freer, more innovative thinking

Re-enchanting the courtyard?

The courtyard at night

A water drop
in the
courtyard

The imaginary part of the courtyard,
invisible and unknown worlds

Under the courtyard

Tell a story

Embellish

Soothing virtue, generating fulfillment > availability for better learning, more empathy, even compassion.

Beyond beauty, the aesthetic value of biodiversity is relational because it exists only through the senses of observer and is largely subjective.

The experience of nature is not only emotional, but also cognitive: naturalist knowledge helps us to better appreciate nature, and modifies our aesthetic perception.

Changing scale, observing ordinary beauty: an aesthetic experience of the miniature wild worlds of the courtyard.

Appropriate > attention

Socio-emotional skills

The garden of empathy

Humans make choices according to their own criteria.

What about the spider's garden? The shrew's garden? The aphid's garden?

Imagine what the garden of the animal that decides on the rest of the living world would be like...

Decentralize.

Consider the rational needs of the Other (appeal to science).

What are the mathematical tools of these other garden inhabitants?

> the spider's web, for example

The courtyard as seen by a spider,
a holm oak, an earthworm...

Questioning our postures to ensure the survival of the Oasis courtyard

Politicize > intention

Common good
Collective interest

MILITANT: collective
commitment to a cause

ETHICS: caring, empathy

EXPERIENTIAL: through contact,
experience, to live something
with, to make memories

From the personal to the common sphere
> openness to others and awareness of
the commons to which we must commit
ourselves

YOURSELF
Personal well-being

Building a collective memory of the history of a common good entrusted to schools

What teachers say:

“To have a life notebook, not necessarily for everyone, but something collective that would be the notebook of life in the courtyard.”

“That we all see the same thing and that we all participate in the same thing.”

Problematize, investigate, explore

A problem occurs when an imbalance occurs that cannot be remedied and that requires research.

Investigation unfolds in a spiral process:

- Construction of the problem, emission of hypotheses, development of their consequences, testing by observation or experimentation, etc.
- The process loops back on itself, with failures forcing us to restructure the problem.

Engage

Inquiry: a process of **problematization** designed to uncover the truth about a tangled issue and re-establish the continuity of an experience.

Social inquiry in the schoolyard has a political aim, requiring a collective response to the problems identified.

This goes beyond children's experiences of nature's objects in their playground.

The Inquiry thus becomes a school learning process, as it involves learning how to deal with problems together, to forge the skills of citizenship in each individual. It is also a way of tackling socially relevant issues at school.

Prospective

Prospective is a modeling founded by philosopher Gaston Berger (1950s)

It's about transforming a future unpredictable and destabilizing into a future predictable and programmable.

Conduct a reflection on the future evolution of eco-socio-systems and deduce actions. It is therefore the future that there is to think about. Approach in scientific rationality.

This project is both philosophical and societal.

Thinking in terms of scenarios > deciding collectively on what is desirable.

Focus on action

Education is the condition of democracy, provided that it is experienced through educational actions that integrate action and reflexivity.

Canguilhem's philosophy: the action is a process of emancipation from established norms and rules.

Educational actions enable the development of proactive individual and collective dispositions > overcoming the main obstacles to commitment: social inhibition (alone I can do nothing) or epistemic inhibition (situation too serious to be changed).

Triggering factors and situations

Under the asphalt, the schoolyard below?

Based on observations in the courtyards and language sessions around facts/processes that are as banal as they are mysterious:

Imagine the path taken by rainwater as it seeps into the ground, to build the water cycle;

Imagine the path of tree roots;

Draw the home of ants that disappear through holes in the ground;

Invent a world based on the mini galleries that burrow into the unfruitfulness of the substrate.

Work on the imaginary, using collective language tools, bodily expression, drawings and writing.

Alternate individual and group situations.

Encourage the search for scientific information to move towards the rational, while admitting to a fantastic dimension that makes people dream.

Complementary artistic and scientific approaches: satisfy curiosity as well as the need for appeasement through beauty and imagination (freeing the mind).

The invisible under the asphalt...

Why is the rainwater stagnating in the yard?

Where is it supposed to go?

Working on the sensitive, the imaginary and the rational.

What's going on beneath our feet, in this invisible world, in the earth... If there is earth...

Invasive wood chips...

Why put shavings in the yard?

Where do the shavings come from?

What will happen to them?

Can small animals live in the shavings?

What's under the shavings?

Can plants grow in the shavings?

Why do I need to replace the shavings?

Treasures in the courtyard

Sacralize the find: a picked-up natural object, belonging to the living or inert world.

Give value to what was lying around the yard: the forgotten, discreet object... but which finds a place of choice in the child's world.

In this way, the playground becomes a space to be explored, full of treasures that help us grow.

Making courtly finds sacred: reviving the curiosity cabinets of the ancients

The Cabinet of Curiosities by Domenico Remps (1690) - Florence

Sacralizing places?

Ritualizing actions?

Sacredness and ritual weave bonds of respect for the living Other

Gardening...

Care in the garden

Caring for ALL living things? Should we feel affection for the other person we have to care for?

And what do we do with what we don't like? The question of what to do with what you don't appreciate > is akin to empathy education. Is there such a thing as reciprocity in care?

When we take care of another human being, in an ideal relationship, we should receive recognition or care in return.

But when we take care of tomato plants or butterflies, what do we get in return? What satisfaction?

A topic to be explored with children through action, words, drawings, storytelling...

Appropriate the genesis of the new courtyard

Work on space and layout, reflecting on the issues at stake for users and decision-makers.

Take up the pupils' yard drawings, and move back and forth between direct observation and interpretation of a plan.

